

EDUCATIONAL ASPIRATIONS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL ADOLESCENTS: ROLE OF PARENTAL EDUCATION AND TYPE OF SCHOOLS

Neha Bhardwaj

Asst. Teacher, DAV Public School, Darbhanga, Bihar,

E-mail ID-nehabhardwaj186@gmail.com

Sesadeba Pany

Associate Professor, Department of Education, Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India,

E-mail ID- sesadeba@cup.edu.in

Kanwaljit Kaur

Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India,

E-mail ID-nanokanwal@gmail.com

Saikalyani Rana

Research Scholar, Department of Education, Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, India,

E-mail ID-ranasaikalyani2018@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 20 SEPT 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 24 OCT 2024

Published On: 01 NOV 2024

Abstract

The current study sought to investigate the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents concerning their parental education and types of schools. In this context, the research study's primary objective was to investigate the levels of educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents, as well as to examine their educational aspirations concerning parental education and the types of schools. The investigator gathered data from 400 adolescents in the government and private schools of Darbhanga, Bihar, India, who were in the 9th and 10th grades. A descriptive research design was implemented by the investigator. The data were collected using the survey method, with the support of a self-developed questionnaire on "Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Adolescents." Chi-square analysis was used to interpret the data. The study's findings revealed that the majority of secondary school students, i.e., 9th and 10th graders, have moderate levels of educational aspirations, and the secondary school adolescents' educational aspirations are independent of their parental education and the type of school. Furthermore, the finding revealed that secondary school boys' educational aspirations are independent of the type of school whereas secondary school girls' educational aspirations are dependent on the type of schools they attend. Based on the study's findings,

it is suggested that special career-related guidance and counseling sessions for both secondary school adolescents and parents may be organized by the school to improve the educational aspirations of the adolescents.

Keywords: *Educational Aspirations, Secondary School Adolescents, Parental Education, Types of Schools*

INTRODUCTION

Education is an ongoing process that begins at birth and continues throughout one's life, with an emphasis on personal development, societal development, and overall development. It is a process of acquiring new knowledge and enhancing one's capacity to think and make decisions. It helps personal growth and society's development. It prepares a child to serve society, the nation, and where they live (Dwivedi, 2022). One can get an education formally as well as informally. Informal education starts from family, friends, and society, and formal education is a systematic approach that starts after a fixed period of years in a school with a planned manner and approach from trained teachers. It is designed to guide students in learning a culture, moulding their behaviour, and directing them toward their eventual societal role. It focuses on an individual's overall development, including overall physical, mental, artistic, intellectual, ethical, spiritual, social, and occupational levels. The education process takes place under the guidance of the teacher in a planned manner with proper pedagogy. Education helps to lead a happy and healthy life. It gives direction to get a desirable job, which leads to earning money for livelihood. It helps in creating a modern society with scientific growth and helps to grow the economy of a state and nation. The nation's educational system has changed significantly throughout the years to meet the increasing needs and demands. India's educational standards have been rising, and many kids are graduating with higher grades as a result of receiving a good education. We can define education as a planned activity formally structured by experts to achieve objectives. It is a process of learning and acquiring knowledge in a formal and informal setting. It helps to enhance critical thinking through different real-life activities taught in a classroom. It starts after birth and continues throughout the life.

The government is trying to encourage the child and their families through schemes and initiatives to educate all students, i.e., boys or girls, tribes, and persons with special needs. Some of the initiatives are 'Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan' for all children between the ages of 6 and 14 years of age. This program was introduced in 2001 to get Universal Elementary Education. 'Midday Meal Scheme' for eliminating classroom hunger, decreasing the dropout ratio of children, and increasing attendance. Right to Education Act for all children from 6 to 14 years

of age. 'Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao' for girls' education and participation in educational activities. 'SAKSHAM' for a person with special needs. All the initiatives taken by the government focus on the nation's growth through education, no one can be discriminated against on the basis of caste, religion, background, and disabilities; everyone has the right to get free and compulsory education, and each school should have facilities for disabled people. An educated person can educate the society.

Indian adolescents face numerous challenges in school, including socioeconomic disparity, systemic barriers, and cultural norms. Another problem is a higher level of competition for jobs and the education system of schools. The lack of properly trained teachers and resources becomes the reason for the lower education aspirations of adolescents. If all schools hire only skill-based and trained teachers for students, then they can easily solve all types of problems of adolescents and encourage critical thinking skills among all adolescents, which can lead to achieving their educational aspirations and overall development of adolescents.

Equitable access to education, career training, and mentorship programs should be given high priority. Educational aspiration is a multidimensional concept that includes the individual's aspirations for learning, educational achievement, and help in future career development. An individual's ambitions and desires to obtain a higher education degree are known as their educational aspirations (Bittmann & Schindler, 2021; Brown et al., 2019). It is like a map, which shows directions or paths to a person. It can be defined as a personal learning objective set by a person. It encompasses the desire to gain knowledge and the determination to overcome challenges and barriers in pursuing educational excellence. Educational aspirations for adolescents indicate the broader area of education, career-related choice, and achievement in a particular skill (Rojewski, 2005; Domina et al., 2011). During adolescence, a person's level of educational aspiration is significantly influenced by their self-concept. In this study, we will concentrate on secondary school adolescents' educational aspirations concerning their parental education and types of schools, which are influenced by a variety of circumstances. Parents' support and encouragement are crucial in influencing their children's educational experience. Parental encouragement positively impacts the overall personality of a student, like motivation, academic performance, and educational goals (Kaplan et al., 2001). Parents' education is beneficial for the improvement of children's educational aspirations, children's intelligence, openness to experience, and children's academic achievement. The education levels of parents have a significant role in predicting the academic and behavioral

Copyright © 2024, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

success of their children (Dearing et al., 2001; Davis-Kean, 2005). The parent's education is a strong pillar of their children's educational outcomes (Eccles, 2005). The high education of fathers and mothers positively influences their students' academic success (Idris et al., 2020). Higher-educated parents have more experience in education, serve as role models and mentors, and provide resources and expertise to support their children in pursuing graduate or college-level education. However, parents with lower education may not be able to resolve their child's learning-related issues. Higher-educated parents are more likely to have the resources and educational expertise at their disposal to support their children in pursuing graduate or college-level education (Spera et al., 2009).

On the other hand, schools significantly influence students' educational aspirations, offering varying opportunities, resources, and experiences. Schools have a big influence on how well students learn and advance; the opportunities that are offered in various schools directly affect students' affective and cognitive behaviors and educational aspirations (Gupta & Bashir, 2017). Government schools, run by government funds, provide free education with standardized norms and curricula. Private schools, run by tuition fees, donations, and other organizations, offer fixed classroom sizes, personalized attention, and more resources. Nevertheless, there is no significant variation in student educational aspirations between government and private schools. School is a critical factor in the development of students' futures. Along with parental education, the types of such adolescents attend also affect their educational aspirations with positive school environments and opportunities influencing academic performance and extracurricular activities. Children who experience positive school environments and chances perform well in both academics and extracurricular activities (Strand & Winston, 2008). Parental encouragement and a good school environment play significant predictors of students' educational aspirations (Yeung & McInerney, 2005; Gupta & Bashir, 2017). The school environment plays a pivotal role in educational aspirations. The academic aspirations of secondary school children are significantly positively correlated with the school environment and parental support (Gupta & Basir, 2017).

Although parental education and school types are considered important factors, there has been a limited amount of research undertaken on the association between parental education and educational aspirations. Student aspirations for education have been proven to be significantly predicted by both the school environment and parental encouragement (Wang & Eccles, 2012; Gupta & Bashir, 2017). It is crucial to examine the interplay between these variables and their impact on the educational aspirations of secondary school students.

Understanding how parent's educational backgrounds and the types of schools they attend influence children's aspirations. Understanding these factors can help policymakers and educators design initiatives to increase students' aspirations for further education.

OBJECTIVES

1. To determine the levels of educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents
2. To explain the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents with reference to their parental education
3. To examine the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents with reference to types of schools
4. To examine the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescent boys with reference to the types of schools
5. To examine the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescent girls with reference to the types of schools

HYPOTHESES

1. The educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents are independent of their parental education.
2. The educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents are independent of the types of schools.
3. The educational aspirations of secondary school adolescent boys are independent of the types of school.
4. The educational aspirations of secondary school adolescent girls are independent of the types of schools.

METHODS AND PROCEDURE

Research Design

The objective of this study is to examine the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents in the Bihar region of India, taking into consideration the parental education and the type of schools. To achieve these objectives, the study utilized an extensive method of gathering data from a large number of participants to make findings. As a result, the investigator used the survey method of descriptive type of research.

Population and Sampling Frame

The population in this study consists of adolescents in the 9th and 10th grades who are currently enrolled in Darbhanga, Bihar, India. According to the UDISE Report 20-21, the total enrolment of adolescents in 9th and 10th grade in Bihar, India is 1,40,455.

Sample of the Study

Data were obtained from 9th and 10th-grade adolescents attending government and private schools connected with the government board and CBSE, New Delhi. The samples were collected from Darbhanga, Bihar. According to the Rao soft sample size calculator, a sample size of 384 is needed to get a 95% confidence level. Nevertheless, data was gathered from a sample of 400 adolescents enrolled in the 9th and 10th grades. The study employed a stratified proportional sampling method keeping in mind the strata like gender and type of school.

TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTIONS

The investigator employed a questionnaire on the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents, which was a self-made tool. The tool was developed covering four dimensions namely personal factor, parental factor, teacher factor, and environment factor. 1st dimension contains 06 items, whereas the 2nd dimension contains 05 items, the 3rd dimension contains 05 items, and the 4th dimension contains 05 items. As a whole, the tool contains a total of 21 items. The items of the tool were validated through expert consultation.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

I. Educational Aspirations Levels of Secondary School Adolescents

The data were obtained from 400 adolescents belonging to 9th and 10th grades and it was found that 87 (21.75%), 191 (47.75%), and 122 (30.5%) adolescents respectively come under low, moderate, and high levels. These data are illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig 1 Level of Educational Aspirations

II. The Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Adolescents and their Parental Education

The second objective was to discuss the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents in relation to their parental education. The current study includes a total of 400 students who are enrolled in the 9th and 10th grades. The data analysis about the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents, regardless of their parental education, has been displayed in Table 1.

Table 1
Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Adolescents Related to their Parental Education

Parental Education →	Illiterate	Below 10 th	Above 10 th	Value of chi-square X^2 (calculated)	Level of significance (table-value)	Remarks
Educational Aspiration ↓						
High	27	69	27	1.68	At 0.05=5.99	Not Significant
Low	70	137	70			

The analysis of the results shown in Table 1 revealed that the acquired value of X^2 (1.68) is smaller than the table value of ' X^2 ', i.e., 5.99 at the 0.05 level of significance with a df value of 2. Therefore, the hypothesis i.e. "*the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents are independent of their parental education*" is accepted. As a result, it may be concluded that secondary school adolescents' educational aspirations are independent of their parents' education. In other words, parental education has no bearing on the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents.

III. The Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Adolescents and the Type of Schools

The third objective was to investigate secondary school adolescents' educational aspirations concerning the type of schools. Table 2 presents the data analysis on secondary school adolescents' educational aspirations concerning their school type.

Table 2
Educational Aspiration of Secondary School Adolescents and the Types of Schools

Type of Schools →	Govt. schools	Private schools	Value of chi-square X^2 (calculated)	Level of significance (table value)	Remarks
Educational Aspirations ↓					
High	110	12	1.65	At 0.05=3.48	Not Significant
Low	238	40			

The analysis of Table 2 demonstrated that the value of X^2 (1.65) obtained is less than the table value of X^2 (3.48) at a 0.05 level of significance with a df value of 1. Therefore, hypothesis i.e., “*the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents are independent of types of school*” is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that the educational aspiration of secondary school adolescents is independent of the types of schools.

IV. The Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Adolescent Boys and the Type of Schools

The study's fourth objective was to analyze the educational aspirations of adolescents in secondary school, specifically concerning the types of schools. The data analysis on the educational aspirations of adolescents in secondary school, regardless of the type of school, has been shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Educational Aspiration of Secondary School Adolescent Boys in relation to the type of School

Types of schools →	Govt. Schools	Private Schools	Value of chi-square X^2 (calculated)	Level of significance (table value)	Remarks
Educational Aspiration of Boys ↓					
High	42	6	0.148	At 0.05=3.48	Not Significant
Low	124	20			

The analysis of Table 3 discovered that the found value of X^2 (0.148) is less than the table value of X^2 i.e. 3.48 at 0.05 level of significance with the df value of 1. Therefore, the hypothesis i.e. *“the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescent boys are independent of the types of school”* is accepted. Hence, it can be inferred that the educational aspiration of secondary school adolescents is independent of the types of schools.

V. The Educational Aspirations of Secondary School Adolescent Girls and the Type of Schools

The fifth objective of the study was to investigate the educational aspirations of adolescent girls in secondary school, specifically concerning the different types of schools. The study of data regarding the educational aspirations of adolescent girls in secondary school concerning their type of schools is displayed in Table 4.

Table 4
Educational Aspiration of Secondary School Adolescent Girls in Relation to the Types of Schools

Types of schools 	Govt. Schools	Private Schools	Value of chi-square X^2 (calculated)	Level of significance (table value)	Remarks
Educational Aspiration of girls 					
High	37	0	7.13	At 0.01=6.635	Significant
Low	145	26			

The result showed that the calculated value of X^2 (7.13) is more than the table value of X^2 i.e. 6.635 at 0.01 level of significance with the df value of 1. Therefore, the hypothesis i.e. *“the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescent girls are independent of the types of school”* is rejected.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

It was observed that 47.75% of secondary school adolescents demonstrate a moderate level of educational aspiration, while 21.75% and 30.50% display low and high levels of educational aspiration respectively. The educational aspiration of secondary school adolescents is independent of parental education. The educational aspiration of secondary school adolescents

is independent of the types of schools. Further, the findings revealed that the secondary school adolescent boys' educational aspirations are independent of the type of school whereas adolescent girls' educational aspirations are dependent on the type of school.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

Adolescents' primary source of aspirations comes from their homes, which support or foster their learning environment. Parents may establish a secure and encouraging home atmosphere that fosters creativity and productivity in their children. Teachers can assist adolescents in finding the correct direction, offer career guidance, and resolve educational issues through diverse academic activities. They can facilitate effective communication in the classroom, instruct and engage in discussions with students, and provide opportunities for practice. To show the different paths for the future selection of courses, it is advisable to organize various career guidance sessions and workshops for adolescents, parents, and teachers. Schools can encourage adolescents to participate in extra-curricular activities for development, motivation, and achievement. Parents can support their adolescents in selecting and setting desirable educational goals and communicating and guiding them promptly so that they can share their education and life-related problems.

CONCLUSIONS

Adolescents' educational aspirations focus on the overall field of education, career choices, and skill achievement. The study suggested that parental education and types of schools do not affect the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents. The educational aspirations of secondary school boys are independent of the types of schools attended. The educational aspirations of secondary school girls are dependent upon the types of schools they attend. Future research may be conducted on other variables related to the educational aspirations of secondary school adolescents, such as self-esteem, peer group, parents' socioeconomic status, community, and health. Establishing more supportive environments can help bridge the disparity in educational aspirations and enable all students to achieve their full potential.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author(s) have disclosed no potential conflicts of interest for the research, writing, and publishing of this paper.

Funding

The author(s) did not get any financial support for conducting research or writing the article.

REFERENCES

- Bittmann, F., & Schindler, S. (2021). *Analysing diversion processes in German secondary education: School-track effects on educational aspirations*. *KZfSS Kölner Zeitschrift für Soziologie und Sozialpsychologie*, 73(2), 231-257. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11577-021-00789-1>
- Brown, A., Waters, C. S., & Shelton, K. H. (2019). *The educational aspirations and psychological well-being of adopted young people in the UK*. *Adoption & Fostering*, 43(1), 46-59.
- Davis-Kean, P. E. (2005). *The influence of parent education and family income on child achievement: the indirect role of parental expectations and the home environment*. *Journal of family psychology*, 19(2), 294. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0893-3200.19.2.294>
- Dearing, E., McCartney, K., & Taylor, B. A. (2001). *Change in family income-to-needs matters more for children with less*. *Child development*, 72(6), 1779-1793.
- Domina, T., Conley, A., & Farkas, G. (2011). *The link between educational expectations and effort in the college-for-all era*. *Sociology of Education*, 84(2), 93-112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1941406411401808>
- Dwivedi, S. (2022). *A comparative study of the level of educational aspiration of secondary school students in Lucknow city*.
- Eccles, J. S. (2005). *Influences of parents' education on their children's educational attainments: The role of parent and child perceptions*. *London review of education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14748460500372309>
- Gupta, S., & Bashir, L. (2017). *Educational aspiration of secondary school students: Influence of school environment and parental encouragement*. *International Journal of Applied Business and Economic Research*, 15(21), 495-507. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00378>
- Idris, M., Hussain, S., & Ahmad, N. (2020). *Relationship between parents' education and their children's academic achievement*. *Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 7(2), 82-92. [https://doi.org/10.46662/jass-vol7-iss2-2020\(82-92\)](https://doi.org/10.46662/jass-vol7-iss2-2020(82-92))
- Kaplan, D. S., Liu, X., & Kaplan, H. B. (2001). *Influence of parents' self-feelings and expectations on children's academic performance*. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 94(6), 360-370. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220670109598773>
- Rojewski, J. W. (2005). *Occupational aspirations: Constructs, meanings, and application*. *Career development and counseling: Putting theory and research to work*, 131-154.
- Spera, C., Wentzel, K. R., & Matto, H. C. (2009). *Parental aspirations for their children's educational attainment: Relations to ethnicity, parental education, children's academic performance, and parental perceptions of school climate*. *Journal of youth and adolescence*, 38, 1140-1152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-008-9314-7>
- Strand, S., & Winston, J. (2008). *Educational aspirations in inner city schools*. *Educational studies*, 34(4), 249-267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055690802034021>
- Wang, M. T., & Eccles, J. S. (2012). *Adolescent behavioral, emotional, and cognitive engagement trajectories in school and their differential relations to educational success*. *Journal of research on adolescence*, 22(1), 31-39. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-7795.2011.00753.x>
- Yeung, A. S., & McInerney, D. M. (2005). *Students' school motivation and aspiration over high school years*. *Educational Psychology*, 25(5), 537-554. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410500046804>